

Synthetic Wheat: A Way Towards New Green Revolution

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Introduction

Wheat is an ancient crop that is still grown as a staple food in many parts of the world. Wheat comes in a variety of varieties, each of which is categorised based on their ploidy level. Common/bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), a hexaploid wheat with 42 chromosomes, is the most widely cultivated. Wheat grain is rich in protein, carbohydrates, lipids, and vitamins, among other nutrients. Wheat is the most important staple food in the world due to its high nutrient content, especially carbohydrates. Global wheat demand is growing in perfect agreement with the world's population, which is projected to increase by 32% by 2050 (Weigand *et al.*, 2011). Using traditional breeding methods, efforts have been made to increase wheat yield. However, after it reached a certain point of change, it remained stagnant. The yield deflation was broken in the 1960s, resulting in a significant increase in wheat productivity. William Gaud coined the term "Green Revolution" to describe this breakthrough.

Wheat production has not improved significantly after a certain degree of improvement, despite the fact that the world population continues to grow. This condition necessitates a new green movement in order to feed the world's rising population. Because of the limited genetic diversity and lack of traits for further improvement, scientists were forced to look for traits in other species. This quest paved the way for synthetic breeding, which offers fresh hope for the coming green revolution.

Synthetic Wheat

The hybridization of *Triticum turgidum* L. with *Aegilops tauschii* produces synthetic wheat (Talbot *et al.*, 2011). The hexaploid synthetic wheat that results serves as a genetic link between wild and cultivated wheat (Calderini *et al.*, 2003 and Ortiz-Monasterio *et al.*, 2003). Primary synthetics are bridging lines used to introduce genetic material from the progenitor species into modern bread wheat (Talbot *et al.*, 2011). The first attempt to produce synthetic wheat was made in the early 1900s with "synthetic spelta" produced during a study to determine the progenitors of *T. aestivum* subsp. spelta. In 1946, Mcfadden and Sears coined the word "synthetic hexaploid wheat" to describe an early allopolyploid hybrid type of bread wheat called Thell (Talbot *et al.*, 2011). After crossing with bread wheat cultivars, the synthetic wheat can be used to produce F1 synthetic derivatives (Trethowan *et al.*, 2008 and Mujeeb-Kazi *et al.*, 2008).

Since the late 1980s, CIMMYT has grown over 1000 primary synthetic wheat cultivars through a wheat wide crossing programme (Lage *et al.*, 2004). Carmona is a CIMMYT synthetic wheat derivative that Spain registered in 2003. This fast-growing variety matures and produces seed faster than most commercial cultivars, which is advantageous for wheat growers in southern Spain who often plant late in the year. Carmona has a higher grain quality and is ideally suited to zero-tillage schemes, where it resists foliar diseases and yields more (Kazi *et al.*, 2004 and Van Ginkel *et al.*, 2004).

Utilization of Synthetic Wheat

Resistance to biotic stresses: The prime synthetics have proven to be a valuable source of disease resistance genetic diversity. Rust is one of the most destructive diseases of wheat worldwide. In synthetic wheat, leaf and stripe rust resistance genes have been discovered. Leaf blotch, glume blotch, crown rot, yellow leaf spot, leaf blight, powdery mildew, and karnal bunt resistance were also demonstrated in synthetic wheat. It also

demonstrated tolerance to insects like the Green bug and the Hessain fly (Van Ginkel et al., 2007 and Ogbonnaya et al., 2007).

Resistance to abiotic stresses: Drought, heat, salinity, and other abiotic stresses were all tolerated well by synthetic wheat. Under drought stress conditions, synthetic wheat yielded 5-40% more in India, Pakistan, Ecuador, and Argentina, as well as Australia (Coghlan et al., 2006). Although the level of genetic variability for salt tolerance has been reported to be restricted in elite bread wheat genotypes due to the source of their D genome, additional genetic variation has been reported in synthetic hexaploid wheat cultivars for salt tolerance (Schachtman et al., 1992). Heat tolerance up to 35-40°C is available in synthetic wheat at the grain filling point (Van Ginkel et al., 2007 and Ogbonnaya et al., 2007).

Pre-harvest sprouting: Pre-harvest sprouting reduces the efficiency of the end product significantly. This is particularly true in areas where there is a lot of rain and a lot of humidity during the harvesting season, resulting in wheat downgrading (Van Ginkel et al., 2007 and Ogbonnaya et al., 2007). There is a connection between seed dormancy and resistance to PHS. Synthetic hexaploid wheat has a lot of genetic variance when it comes to seed dormancy.

Yield and yield components: In yield trials conducted between 2001 and 2003, synthetic wheat achieved higher yields than common wheat. These tests revealed that synthetic wheat derivatives are globally competitive and adaptable in both specific and large ways (Villareal et al., 1994). In synthetic wheat, there is a positive association between high grain yield, improved harvest index, improved grain weight, and increased above ground biomass (Rathey et al., 2011).

Conclusion

More wheat is needed around the world to meet the growing population's food needs. While wheat production has increased, there has been no perceptible increase in wheat per acre yield in the last 15-20 years. Several programmes have been launched around the world to develop high-yielding wheat cultivars, but only a few have recorded success. A team of scientists from Cambridge University's National Institute of Agricultural Botany (NIAB) announced a breakthrough in the production of high-yielding wheat, dubbed "super wheat." According to NIAB sources, these scientists say that their newly developed "super wheat" would yield 30% more than current wheat cultivars. As a result, this wheat can be considered a watershed moment in the history of synthetic wheat, as it will be the first commercialised type of synthetic wheat.

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